

germination even at 20 ppm Zn. Values for vigor, which is considered a reliable index of seed potency, indicated that all the varieties performed best at 5 ppm Zn. Higher concentrations (15 and 20

ppm) reduced Jaya and IR20 vigor, but not that of Kanchi (see table). EC of the seed leachates after soaking in Zn was negatively correlated with

germination and seedling vigor. Zn had little effect on endosperm weight, but germination percentage was closely related to seed treatment. *S*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization HYBRID RICE

Ratoon regeneration in rices and their single-cross hybrids after three cuttings

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Sixteen single-cross hybrids of 15 rice varieties were planted in Aug 1982 at Main Research Station, Bangalore. F2 seeds were harvested on 24 Jan, 20 Aug, and 10 Dec 1983. After the third ratooning, stubble was left in situ or transplanted in single rows containing 30 slips. Thirty-five days after cutting and transplanting, plant height and number of tillers per plant were recorded (see table). Plant height was measured from the ground to the tip of the topmost leaf.

Hybrids had greater regeneration capacity than varieties. Hybrid TNI/Type 3 had the best regeneration ability. Among varieties, Type 3 had good regeneration. Many varieties could not be propagated in situ after the third cutting. Vegetative propagation of

Plant height and tillers per plant on 20 plants 35 d after thud cutting.

	Plant height (cm)		Tillers (no.)	
	In situ	Transplanted	In situ	Transplanted
<i>Cross</i>				
TNI/Type 3	56.2±3.6	67.4±1.7	24.7±4.0	14.8±4.7
Jaya/Type 3	54.9±1.9	53.0±1.4	31.9±5.5	7.2±0.4
PK150/Basumathi	54.5±3.6	21.0±3.5	31.1±4.1	2.0±0.4
Mashuri/Doddi	51.1±1.4	45.9±2.5	19.1±3.1	3.6±0.4
Mashuri/Prakash	46.9±1.9	39.8±2.3	22.2±3.7	5.4±0.5
IET7031/Telahamsa	44.1±1.8	35.1±2.6	20.4±2.9	1.9±0.5
SHM 1/Intan Mutant 1	44.2±1.7	32.8±8.6	7.1±1.4	3.3±0.5
Type 3/Telahamsa	44.3±1.8	47.0±1.5	22.8±1.6	10.5±0.7
TNI/Telahamsa	39.4±1.4	30.1±1.5	18.3±2.2	3.8±0.7
Jaya/Telahamsa	35.6±2.1	30.5±4.2	12.3±1.5	2.6±0.5
Jaya/Mashuri	38.5±1.3	34.3±1.7	20.3±2.7	4.8±0.5
Jaya/IET7031	38.4±2.3	32.3±2.4	16.0±1.1	2.5±0.5
PK150/IR36	37.9±2.6	28.2±1.9	18.2±1.9	4.4±0.6
Mangla/Telahamsa	37.1±0.9	33.4±1.6	19.0±3.2	3.0±0.4
PK177/Intan Mutant 1	36.8±1.5	34.6±1.3	14.2±1.5	5.1±0.6
IET7031/Mangla	36.4±4.3	30.6±2.9	6.6±3.9	3.1±0.6
<i>Variety</i>				
Type 3	52.3±3.9	53.9±2.1	14.8±2.6	3.8±0.4
Jaya	29.8±3.5	31.7±2.1	7.7±0.9	3.2±0.4
Mangla	36.7±2.9	34.3±1.9	3.7±2.2	4.2±0.3
Telahamsa	37.4±0.9	27.2±1.6	15.3±3.1	2.5±0.3
Mashuri	42.4±2.2	36.4±1.6	—	4.3±0.4
TNI	—	29.1±1.9	—	4.1±0.5
Prakash	—	34.3±2.1	—	4.7±0.4
Intan Mutant 1	—	45.3±2.6	—	4.7±0.7
Doddi	—	50.6±1.5	—	3.9±0.7

single-cross hybrids allows continuous production of F2 seeds and maximizes

the population size of the second segregating generation of any cross. *S*

Performance of male-sterile and maintainer lines and crosses

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We evaluated Chinese cytoplasmic male-sterile (cms) lines V20A and Zhen Shan 97A and corresponding maintainers V20B and Zhen Shan 97B in 1983 wet and 1984 dry season at CLDRRI. In wet season, they matured early and had low phenotypic acceptability (scale 5),

Table 1. Agronomic traits of cms lines and maintainers at O Mon, Hau Giang, Vietnam.

Line	Duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles/m ²	Grains/panicle	Sterility (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Yield (t/ha)
<i>1983 wet season</i>							
V20A	89	75	304				
V20B	91	67	274	74	38	29	2.9
Zhen Shan 97A	93	73	218				
Zhen Shan 97B	97	69	212	137	27	27	2.2
<i>1984 dry season</i>							
V20A	90	71	363				
V20B	97	71	284	74	16	30	2.3
Zhen Shan 97A	93	68	297				
Zhen Shan 97B	103	74	269	97	26	28	2.8